

ASSESSING KIDNEY FUNCTION IN ELDERLY**Stițiu Irina,***Student, Faculty of General Medicine,
State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemițanu"
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Boris Sasu***Doctor of medical sciences, Associate professor,
The Discipline of Rheumatology and Nephrology,
State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemițanu"
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Abstract**

In recent years, due to the increase in life expectancy in Western societies, there has been such an unprecedented phenomenon - a sharp increase in the proportion of elderly people aged 65 years and older. The main direction that will significantly affect the daily professional life of nephrologists in the 21st century is the progressive aging of the world's population. Therefore, plans to integrate nephrology with gerontology and geriatrics will allow these sciences to adapt to this inevitable phenomenon of increasing demographic pressure and manage health and care at all levels - from the individual patient to the general population and global health systems.

Aim of the study: To study the prevalence and characteristics of functional changes in the kidneys in elderly and senile people for the early implementation of preventive actions.

Keywords: Aging, Kidney function, Glomerular filtration rate, Chronic kidney disease

Introduction

Aging is a comprehensive process that is caused by many factors and their action, in turn, is repeated and accumulated throughout life. These are stress, past illnesses, accumulation of toxins and free radicals, depletion of stem cells, exposure to xenobiotics (foreign substances), temperature damage, insufficient excretion of protein breakdown products, lack of vitamins and microelements, hypoxia, and others [5,6].

In addition, aging is a multifocal process that occurs in different cell structures: in the nucleus, membranes, in different types of cells: nervous, secretory, immune, renal, and others [4].

Undoubtedly, aging is associated with a decrease in physiological homeostasis. This multidimensional phenomenon encompasses physical, psychological and social changes. In higher organisms, aging homeostasis is regulated by the interaction of many organs. With age, dysfunction of one organ can lead to functional failure of many organs [5].

It is well known that both the number of past diseases and chronic diseases increase with age. Urological diseases such as nephropathy (such as pyelonephritis, polycystic kidney disease, diabetic or hypertensive nephropathy, etc.), adenoma and prostate cancer, urinary incontinence, etc occupy a large percentage of them. In an aging body, damage to various structures occurs: collagen, cell membranes, DNA and other molecules, cells and tissues [2,3,7].

Aging is an inevitable process of life for all living beings. However, data from longitudinal studies suggest that one third of all healthy people aged 23–97 years are practically not affected by changes in kidney function throughout their lives [1].

Materials and methods

To achieve the goal of the study, a group of 50 patients was retrospectively selected, of which 34 were women and 16 were men. Their age ranged from 60 to

90 years, the average age was 71.8 ± 7 years. Patients were treated in the Department of Nephrology at the IMSP SCM "Holy Trinity", Chisinau, in 2022.

The following data was extracted from the observation sheets:

- Clinical data (medical history, BMI, sex, age, main diagnosis, concomitant diagnosis, presence of hypertension, risk factors for BCR)
- Paraclinical data (general blood test, biochemical blood test, urinalysis, calculation of GFR, results of ultrasound of the kidneys).

Research methods

The study is based on the following research methods: historical, descriptive. Primary data collection methods are based on medical records (patient records) using official statistics. Statistical processing of the results of the study was carried out by computerized methods of analysis of variations using special programs (Microsoft Excell 2013 for Windows).

Results

In both age groups, approximately the same percentage of men and women with pathology of the nephro-urinary system appears.

- 67.64% of women are aged 60-74,
- 32.35% belong to the age group of 75-90 years,
- 0% of women are in the 90+ age group.
- 68.75% of the men who underwent the study were aged 60-74 years,
- 31.25% - in the age group of 75-90 years,
- 0% of men are in the 90+ age group.

1. Characteristics of diseases of the urinary system in the elderly and senile age

Among the nephropathologies that patients of elderly and senile age suffered from, the most common was chronic pyelonephritis in the acute stage - 92%. In 28% of 50 patients, solitary or multiple cysts were

found on echography. And 8% of patients had uni-/bilateral hydronephrosis. Glomerulonephritis was rarely detected - only 2% of cases.

Among all concomitant diseases, the prevalence of arterial hypertension is 48%, various forms of heart disease (ischemic, hypertensive or mixed) - in 40% of patients. 32% of patients had anemia of renal or other

origin. Diabetes mellitus type 2 was in the stage of compensation or undercompensation in 30% of patients. There is obesity of class 1 and 2 in 20% of patients, nephrolithiasis confirmed by ultrasound - in 8%. Hyperuricemia was present in 4% of cases, cystitis - in 4% (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Disease prevalence by age and sex 1

2. Prevalence of the disease by age and sex

The diagram below shows the prevalence of diseases that are risk factors for the development and progression of BCR (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Distribution by diseases that elderly and senile patients suffered from

3. Estimated GFR < 60 ml/min over 1.73 m²

Glomerular filtration rate (GFR) is estimated using an equation developed by the Collaborative Organization for the Epidemiology of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD-EPI).

Of the 50 patients, only 18 people, including 5 elderly and 13 senile patients, had GFR > 60 ml/min over an area of 1.73 m². The prevalence of reduced kidney function (estimated GFR < 60 ml/min per 1.73 m²) was in 32 patients.

Moreover, the trend of increasing prevalence of renal dysfunction with age was observed mainly in

women. Thus, GFR < 60 ml/min per 1.73 m² was determined in 69% of women and 63% of elderly men and in 91% of women and 60% of men of senile age.

4. Prevalence of CKD

Among patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), the stage of the disease should be determined by the level of renal function according to the KDOQI CKD classification.

Overall, 64% of participants had CKD and were predominantly in CKD stages III (11 women and 2 men) and IV (6 women and 5 men), with a female predominance. The prevalence of CKD stage V according to KDOQI was 4 women and 4 men, of which 2 men and only 1 woman of senile age (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Prevalence of CKD in elderly and senile patients

Conclusion

The population of the planet is rapidly aging, and with age, the functionality of the kidneys proportionally fades. It is also clear that GFR itself is an indicator of accelerated aging. In this sense, the practical benefits of research work are important for the medical community, whose goal is to ensure the prevention and diagnosis of renal pathology at any age, especially in the elderly, the prevention of concomitant complications and, thus, the prolongation of the quality of care in old age and active life.

References

1. Baba M, Shimbo T, Horio M, Ando M, Yasuda Y, Komatsu Y, Masuda K, Matsuo S, Maruyama S. Longitudinal Study of the Decline in Renal Function in Healthy Subjects. *PLoS One*. 2015 Jun 10;10(6):e0129036.

2. Budylev S.A., Selivanov A.N., Perelygin K.V., Mudrakovskaya E.V., *Fundamental research-2014.-No.10(part 10)-1902-1906*

3. Denic A, Glassock RJ, Rule AD. Structural and Functional Changes With the Aging Kidney. *Adv Chronic Kidney Dis*. 2016 Jan;23(1):19-28.

4. Di Micco R, Krizhanovsky V, Baker D, d'Adda di Fagagna F. Cellular senescence in ageing: from mechanisms to therapeutic opportunities. *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol*. 2021 Feb;22(2):75-95.

5. Pomatto LCD, Davies KJA. The role of declining adaptive homeostasis in ageing. *J Physiol*. 2017 Dec 15;595(24):7275-7309.

6. Rahal A, Kumar A, Singh V, Yadav B, Tiwari R, Chakraborty S, Dhama K. Oxidative stress, prooxidants, and antioxidants: the interplay. *Biomed Res Int*. 2014;2014:761264.

7. Weinstein JR, Anderson S. The aging kidney: physiological changes. *Adv Chronic Kidney Dis*. 2010 Jul;17(4):302-7.